

Distributed Sequential Cloud-Native Deployment of an End-to-End 5G Network with O-RAN Functions

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Abstract—The exploitation of novel networking paradigms to manage next-generation mobile networks is essential to meet the requirements of emerging use cases and scenarios. In this demonstration, we showcase a comprehensive end-to-end cloud-native open-source deployment of a 5G mobile network incorporating O-RAN functionality. Spanning across distributed points of presence, this demonstration features a disaggregated and sequential deployment of mobile entities, enabling seamless adaptation to the availability and distribution of computational resources. We highlight the on-demand plug-and-play of different monitoring xApp instances to show the flexibility of the deployment process as a critical enabler towards more autonomous orchestration procedures aimed at optimizing network performance.

Index Terms—B5G/6G, O-RAN, Management and Orchestration, Cloud-Native, Disaggregation, Open5GS, srsRAN, FlexRIC

I. INTRODUCTION

The architecture of next-generation mobile networks is undergoing a significant transformation, driven by the introduction of recent networking paradigms based on virtualization/cloudification and the adoption of open interfaces. These features facilitate the disaggregation of monolithic functions into distinct network functions (NFs) and the separation of control and user planes, providing the needed flexibility and dynamicity to customise mobile network deployments. Such deployments can be tailored to satisfy the requirements of challenging use cases and scenarios proposed by vertical industries, potentially leading to new business models, like the development of Non-Public Networks.

Such a trend, initially introduced in the mobile core segment with the adoption of the Service Based Architecture (SBA), is being developed in the radio access network (RAN) segment, where Open RAN (O-RAN) alliance [1] proposes an architecture based on disaggregation and softwarisation to naturally include close-loop operations enhancing the performance of the network while promoting interoperability among multi-vendor providers. In this context, it is essential to define appropriate management and orchestration (MANO) procedures to automate such deployments, ensuring an efficient use of computing, memory, and network resources distributed across different points of presence (PoPs).

This work has received funding from Spanish MINECO grants TSI-063000-2021-56/TSI-063000-2021-57 (6G-BLUR SMART/6G-BLUR JOINT), from EU Horizon 2020 grant agreement No 951867 (5G-ROUTES), Grant PID2021-126431OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe” and Generalitat de Catalunya grant 2021 SGR 00770.

In this demonstration, we dig into MANO procedures following a fully cloud-native approach to offer a flexible deployment of an end-to-end mobile network integrating O-RAN components, like the near-Real Time (near-RT) Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC) and the xApps. These components enable the monitoring of gNB parameters via the E2 interface and allow for the implementation of actions to modify the gNB configuration, aiming to adapt and enhance network performance as defined in the O-RAN specifications [1].

Our experimental deployment is based on open-source software due to its flexibility, re-usability, and cost. The literature includes examples of open-source mobile core deployments using cloud-native tools, such as Kubernetes [2], [3]. However, the distribution of NFs of the mobile core is predefined, static and deployed all at once, lacking the flexibility to further redefine the deployment. Regarding the RAN segment, to the best of our knowledge, a cloud-native orchestration approach has yet to be explored in the literature. Indeed, current end-to-end mobile network setups considering O-RAN entities, execute RAN entities, such as the gNB, the near-RT RIC or the xApp, using command line interface directly from the involved hosts [4], [5].

In contrast, this demonstration shows the first practical disaggregated, distributed, and sequential deployment of an end-to-end open-source cloud-native mobile network from RAN to Core, including some entities introduced by the O-RAN architecture. The multiple pieces of this deployment can be deployed strategically to make an efficient use of the resources available in the PoPs while satisfying latency constraints imposed by the operations and procedures of the different entity instances. Given that the control plane of the mobile core can be placed in a central PoP, the provider can later choose different locations for the user plane, the gNodeB (gNB), the RIC, and corresponding xApps to be distributed among available edge PoPs. All these entities are treated as individual Network Services (NSs), employing an ETSI NFV MANO platform to facilitate the operation of the setup. Thus, it enhances the automation, flexibility and portability capabilities of the deployment process by keeping track of the many configuration and executable files to configure the whole end-to-end mobile network. As well, it facilitates the continuous adaptation of the network to evolving requirements, supporting the on-demand creation and deletion of different entities, such as User Plane Functions (UPFs), gNBs or xApps to enable data-driven close-loops orchestration procedures.

Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 illustrates the experimental setup deployed in the EXTREME® xG Testbed located in CTTC (Castelldefels, Spain). This MANO framework is distributed among three commercial-of-the-shelf servers. One server runs an instance of ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM) Release 14 and the two remaining servers act as PoPs, where a single-node Kubernetes cluster in each PoP acts as a Container Infrastructure Manager (CIM). The framework deploys the NS definitions associated to the mobile network entities at the two PoPs, representing a cloud and an edge location. Concerning the RAN equipment, the setup counts with a USRP B210 device acting as a radio frontend for over-the-air (OTA) transmission connected to the edge PoP. As OTA UE, the setup counts with a Realme 9 smartphone connected to a laptop for being interfaced via a graphical remote desktop tool.

This demonstration aims at showing the capabilities of this framework to feature a disaggregated fully cloud-native deployment of i) Open5GS [6] acting as mobile core, ii) srsRAN [7] project acting as gNB and iii) FlexRIC [8] framework implementing a near-RT RIC and associated xApps. Five configuration blueprints (i.e., Helm charts) have been developed for this end. Two blueprints are for the disaggregated deployment of the 5G mobile core (Open5GS v2.6.4) NFs [9]: one blueprint contains the Kubernetes’ manifests to deploy the control-plane functions (i.e., AMF, AUSF, BSF, NRF, NSSF, PFC, UDM, UDR, SMF and associated database), and the other blueprint consists of the manifest belonging to the user-plane functions (i.e., UPF). Then, there is a blueprint for deploying an srsRAN joint CU/DU gNB instance (srsRAN Release 24.04). This manifest is prepared to configure and launch OTA transmission through the USRP B210 device. The remaining two blueprints are devoted to the FlexRIC framework (*br-flexric* branch Release 24.05). More specifically, one blueprint defines the deployment of the near-RT RIC component, while the other blueprint allows the deployment of

a monitoring xApp enabling the selection of gNB parameters to monitor.

The flexible templating capabilities of Helm charts allow the parameterization of the different blueprints. To enable the distributed deployment in multiple clusters and the compatibility with other SW/HW components, the blueprints need to provide access for some NF pods exposing standard ports defined in 3GPP specifications. For such external access, blueprints use the Kubernetes *LoadBalancer* service type¹. Specifically, the mobile core control-plane blueprint exposes the AMF and SMF NFs pods. The mobile core user-plane blueprint exposes the UPF pod to establish the handshake with SMF through N4 interface using an SCTP connection for the *pcf* protocol (port 8805) and a UDP connection for the *gtpu* protocol (port 2152). The gNB blueprint exposes the created pod to establish a handshake with the AMF, and the UPF specified by SMF upon a UE association request, through the N2 and N3 interfaces using port 38412 for SCTP and port 2152 for GTP connections, respectively. The near-RT RIC blueprint exposes the created pod so gNB can send the messages to it and the monitoring xApp blueprint can retrieve the measurements through the E2 interface using two SCTP connections running on ports 36421 and 36422, respectively.

These blueprints are packaged in OSM descriptors (VNF and NS packages). The available parameterization in these blueprints allows the creation of appropriate configuration files to feed OSM instantiation commands, thus enabling the on-demand and generic creation of instances of such entities.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the distributed, disaggregated, and on-demand deployment of a fully cloud-native 5G mobile network, considering core and O-RAN components packaged as different NSs. Initially, the multiple descriptors

¹For the inter-pod communication within the same blueprint (e.g., Open5GS control-plane NFs) not requiring external exposition, *ClusterIP* type of services are used.

Fig. 2. Layout of the graphical visualization of the demonstration

containing the disaggregated 5G core and O-RAN components are onboarded into the OSM MANO stack. Then, the main steps of the demonstration are:

- 1) We request OSM to deploy the Open5GS control-plane NS in the cloud PoP. In the configuration of the SMF NF, we define a data network (e.g., *mecnet*). Once deployed, the UE information is registered in the UDR database of Open5GS.
- 2) The Open5GS user-plane NS is deployed by OSM in edge clusterB. This UPF is configured to reach the deployed SMF.
- 3) OSM receives the request to deploy the FlexRIC near-RT RIC NS also in cluster B.
- 4) We request OSM to deploy the SRS gNB NS also in clusterB, where the USRP B210 HW is connected. This gNB is configured to reach the AMF placed in the cloud PoP and the near-RT RIC already deployed.
- 5) Now, we proceed to register the UE in the network. After leaving the flight mode, the UE receives an IP address in the range of *mecnet*. We trigger traffic generation from the UE by requesting videos in a commercial video-streaming app (e.g., YouTube).
- 6) We request OSM to deploy a first monitoring xApp NS instance in clusterB, close to the near-RT RIC². This xApp instance follows the downlink throughput at the gNB.
- 7) Finally, OSM is requested to deploy a second monitoring xApp NS instance in clusterB. This new xApp instance is configured to follow the uplink throughput at the gNB.

During the demonstration, all steps are shown through the graphical user interface of OSM, the remote desktop session with the Realme9 smartphone and the logs provided by the different containerised NFs, as shown in Figure 2. A

²It is worth mentioning that due to the way this blueprint is defined, the xApp could be deployed in another cluster while having network connectivity to the cluster where the FlexRIC near-RT instance is running.

demonstration video is available online³.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This demonstration showcases a distributed and on-demand deployment of a cloud-native 5G mobile network, encompassing both Core and RAN functionalities, with a specific focus on deploying O-RAN entities such as near-RT RIC and xApps to facilitate adaptive monitoring. The deployment strategy is based on designing and implementing effective descriptors that leverage orchestration tools like OSM and Kubernetes, thereby enabling flexible and automated deployment capabilities. This approach empowers B5G/6G network management to dynamically adapt and scale according to operational requirements, facilitating autonomous orchestration decisions driven by closed-loop feedback mechanisms.

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³Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XYtJnSY6N8>